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Title: Harnessing Generative AI for Innovative Instruction, Research and Extension: Towards Crafting of Policies for Responsible Use

Proponents

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Abstract

This study explored the types of generative AI tools being used, how widely they are applied, their responsible use, and their impact on learning and critical thinking. A mixed-method approach was used, with data collected from faculty and students through researcher-designed Likert Scale questionnaires. The study also reviewed existing AI policies from participating universities. Results showed that students and teachers are using generative AI tools, with ChatGPT (OpenAI) being the most popular. However, their use is still limited, showing that AI is not yet fully integrated into academic activities. Respondents showed good awareness of ethical use, but there is still a need to protect academic integrity and ensure equal access. AI was found to moderately support learning and critical thinking, but it should be used alongside traditional learning methods. Many universities already have AI policies, highlighting the need for Saint Mary's University to create its own clear and accessible policy. A proposed AI policy with nine key sections was created, based on the university's Catholic values, promoting ethical growth, innovation, and responsible use. The study recommends that Saint Mary's University evaluate and adopt this policy to meet the needs of students, teachers, and staff. This will help guide fair and ethical AI use, maintain academic standards, support real learning, and provide regular training and updates.

Keywords: Academic integrity, authorship, AI-giarism, critical thinking, extent of use

Introduction

A. Short Introduction

Philippine Education is committed to improving the holistic development of Filipino children, preparing them for the evolving demands of society (Bernido, 2021). However, literacy in the Philippines challenges in improving student comprehension and critical thinking skills. In response, educational technology can help Filipino students develop better critical thinking skills (Brazel, 2020). Generative Artificial Intelligence or AI is rapidly transforming several sectors and education is not an exemption. Generative AI such as chatbots is increasingly being used in higher education. Nevertheless, their usage presents positive and negative implications (Nguyen-Duc, et al. 2023). AI can increase the efficiency and accuracy

of teachers in tasks such as making lessons, tests, and activities and computing students' grades (Harry, 2023). But, the use of AI can also raise ethical and academic integrity concerns (Gallent Torres, et al., 2023). The impact of these tools on traditional assessment methods is particularly important, prompting the need for critical assessment and policy guidelines (Lievens, 2023)

B. Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

This study determined how universities reacted and applied generative artificial intelligence (AI) in their instruction, research, and extensions.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following:

1. What generative AI tools are used by the students and teachers?
2. What is the extent of use of the students and teachers in generative AI?
3. What is meant by the responsible use of AI concerning the following:
 - a. Instruction
 - b. Research and Extension
4. How can we promote academic integrity and authorship even with the aid of AI?
5. What is the perceived impact of AI on learning and critical thinking?
6. What are the policies of other institutions in the responsible use of AI?
7. What Policy on the Responsible use of AI can be proposed for Saint Mary's University based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-method design and was conducted in 16 selected universities in the Philippines, particularly those affiliated with the National Consortium. The participants included both faculty and students, with a target sample size of at least 30 students and 5 faculty members per university. However, in one university, only policy review was allowed instead of questionnaire administration. Data collection involved researcher-made four-point Likert Scale questionnaires designed to assess the extent of generative AI use, its perceived impact on learning and critical thinking, and the responsible use of AI in instruction, research, and extension. These instruments underwent validity testing, and their internal consistency was verified using Cronbach's Alpha, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Main Variable, Cronbach's Alpha and Number of Item

Main Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
Generative AI Tools Used by Students and Teachers and the Extent of Use of Generative AI	.700	4
Responsible Use of AI in Education	.971	10
Promoting Academic Integrity and Authorship with AI	.974	25
Perceived Impact of AI on Learning and Critical Thinking	.962	25

Treatment of Data

Descriptive Statistics such as percent, mean and standard deviations were computed. Tables 2 -4 shows the guide for interpretation.

Table 2 shows the mean range, qualitative description, and interpretation of the extent of the responsible use of AI.

Table 2. Mean Range, Qualitative Description, and Interpretation of the Extent of Responsible Use of AI

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
1.00-1.49	Very Not Responsible Use
1.50-2.49	Not Responsible Use
2.50-3.49	Responsible Use
3.50-4.00	Very Responsible Use

Table 3 shows the mean range, qualitative description, and interpretation of the extent of adherence to academic integrity when using AI.

Table 3. Mean Range, Qualitative Description, and Interpretation of the Extent of Adherence to Academic Integrity When using AI

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
1.00-1.49	Very Poor Adherence
1.50-2.49	Poor Adherence
2.50-3.49	Good Adherence
3.50-4.00	Excellent Adherence

Table 4 shows the mean range, qualitative description, and interpretation of the extent of impact of using AI on learning and critical thinking.

Table 4. Mean Range, Qualitative Description, and Interpretation of the Extent of Impact of Using AI on Learning and Critical Thinking

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
1.00-1.49	No Perceived Impact
1.50-2.49	Low Perceived Impact
2.50-3.49	Moderate Perceived Impact
3.50-4.00	High Perceived Impact

Moreover, using the results of the Likert scale and the existing policies of the universities that are members of the National Consortium, data were triangulated through document review. The policies of the consortium universities served as the basis for crafting the policy on the responsible use of AI at Saint Mary's University, with integration of the University's Vision and Mission.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB). Although the authors are affiliated with the 16 selected universities, they did not participate in the survey to avoid conflict of interest. All data were treated with strict confidentiality, and participant identities were anonymized or pseudonymized, with access limited to authorized researchers. Informed consent was obtained, participation was voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw anytime. Vulnerable individuals were given extra protections, and those unable or unwilling to respond were excluded. Potential

risks, such as emotional discomfort or confidentiality breaches, were minimized through ethical safeguards. Participants contributed to the development of a responsible AI use policy, benefiting both the academic community and Saint Mary's University. Study findings will be shared through publications, conferences, and accessible formats for participants.

Result and Discussion

Section 1. generative AI tools are used by the students and teachers

Table 5 presents the percent of generative AI tools utilized by students and teachers.

Table 5. The Generative AI Tools Used by the Students and Teachers

Generative AI	Student	Teacher	Overall
ChatGPT (OpenAI)	94.4	91.7	93.3
Gemini AI	72.2	91.7	80
Quillbolt	83.3	91.7	86.7
Ellicit AI	77.8	83.3	80
Others, pls specify.	Grammarly		
	Perplexity		
	DeepSeek		

As shown in Table 5, more than 50% of teachers and students reported using the listed generative AI tools. ChatGPT (OpenAI) emerged as the most frequently used, with 94.4% of students and 91.7% of teachers indicating its use, yielding an overall usage rate of 93.3%. In addition to the specified tools, respondents also mentioned the use of other platforms such as Grammarly, Perplexity, and DeepSeek.

The data further reveals that students and teachers actively use various generative AI tools to support their academic tasks. There is a notable preference for applications that assist in content generation, writing enhancement, and research facilitation. The high adoption rates across both groups indicate increasing familiarity with and acceptance of generative AI technologies in educational contexts.

Section 2. The extent of use of students and teachers in generative AI

Table 6 presents the extent of use of various generative AI tools by students and teachers.

Table 6. Extent of Use of Students and Teachers in Generative AI

Generative AI	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Description
ChatGPT (OpenAI)	2.79	.787	High Extent
Gemini AI	1.92	.974	Low Extent
Quillbolt	2.58	1.027	High Extent
Ellicit AI	2.00	1.063	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.29	.791	Low Extent

Table 6 shows that respondents used ChatGPT (Mean = 2.79, SD = 0.787) and Quillbolt (Mean = 2.58, SD = 1.027) to a high extent, while Gemini AI (Mean = 1.92, SD = 0.974) and Ellicit AI (Mean = 2.00, SD = 1.063) were used to a low extent. The overall mean usage of generative AI tools was 2.29 (SD = 0.791), corresponding to a low extent of use.

This indicates that although respondents reported using generative AI tools, not all were utilized to a high extent, suggesting selective or limited integration of certain tools in their academic activities.

Section 3. The responsible use of AI

Table 7. Mean, Standard Deviations, and Qualitative Descriptions of Responsible Use of AI

Domains	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Instruction	3.060	.7863	Responsible Use
Research and Extension	2.960	.7780	Responsible Use

The result shows that students and teachers used AI responsibly in instruction and research extension.

Section 4 . How to promote academic integrity and authorship even with the aid of AI

Table 8. Adherence in promoting academic integrity and authorship with the aid of AI

Domains	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Understanding and Awareness of Academic Integrity in AI Use	3.133	.7014	Good Adherence
AI Tool Usage and Ethical Considerations	3.267	.661	Good Adherence
Institutional Policies and Academic Integrity	2.93	.783	Good Adherence
Authorship and AI Use in Academic Work	3.16	.719	Good Adherence
Safeguarding Academic Integrity in the Age of AI	3.09	.822	Good Adherence

The results indicate that both students and teachers demonstrated good adherence across all domains

Section 5. Perceived impact of AI on learning and critical thinking

Table 9. Perceived Impact on Learning and Critical Thinking

Domains	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Impact of AI on Learning	3.01	.815	Moderate Perceived Impact
AI's Role in Enhancing Learning Engagement	2.81	.751	Moderate Perceived Impact
Impact of AI on Critical Thinking	2.87	.783	Moderate Perceived Impact
AI's Influence on Independent Thinking	2.86	.730	Moderate Perceived Impact
Concerns About AI's Potential Impact on Critical Thinking	3.07	.769	Moderate Perceived Impact

The result shows that teachers and students AI had moderate impact on learning and critical thinking.

Section 6. The policies of other institutions on the responsible use of AI

Table 19. Frequency and Percent of Universities with Policies and Without Policies

	Frequency	Percent
No confirmation yet	7	43.75
With Online Policy	4	25
With Policy	5	31.25

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Table 19 reveals that 43.75% of universities have not confirmed the existence of AI-related policies, 25% have accessible online policies, and 31.25% have existing policies. These findings highlight the need for Saint Mary's University to develop a clear and accessible policy on the ethical and responsible use of AI.

Section 7. Proposed Policy on the Responsible use of AI

Proposed Policy on the Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)
Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

1. PURPOSE

This policy explains how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be used in a good and helpful way at Saint Mary's University. It guides students, teachers, staff, and researchers in using AI responsibly—helping people make better decisions, improve learning, and stay true to the values of our Catholic faith, including excellence, innovation, and service to others through Christ.

2. WHO SHOULD FOLLOW THIS POLICY

Everyone at SMU—students, teachers, researchers, staff, and partners—should follow this policy whenever they use AI in school, research, work, or online activities.

3. IMPORTANT GUIDELINES

When using AI at Saint Mary's University, everyone should follow these principles:

- a. **AI Supports, Not Replaces People**
 AI is a helpful tool, but people must still think, create, and decide. Everyone is responsible for their own work and must follow Christian values.
- b. **Be Honest and Clear**
 Always say if AI helped you with a task. Tell how you used it. This builds trust and fairness.
- c. **Be Fair and Respectful**
 Use AI in a way that respects all people and avoids discrimination. Everyone should have equal access to AI tools.
- d. **Learn and Research Honestly**
 Don't use AI to cheat or copy. Students must think and learn on their own, while researchers must ensure that their findings are truthful and original.
- e. **Protect Private Information**
 Do not share private or sensitive information with AI tools. Always follow data privacy rules.
- f. **Use AI for Good**
 Use AI to improve lives, help others, and support the university's mission to serve both local and global communities.

4. ALLOWED AND ENCOURAGED USES OF AI

- a. Students may use Generative AI (GenAI) tools to support their writing, studying, and idea organization. However, they are expected to think critically and produce original work. Directly copying and pasting AI-generated content and presenting it

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as one's own constitutes plagiarism. The use of GenAI is comparable to relying on another person to complete academic tasks or assessments; therefore, proper attribution is mandatory when GenAI tools are used.

- b. Teachers may utilize AI tools to support lesson planning and activity development, as long as the learning objectives prioritize the cultivation of students' critical thinking and independent learning. Faculty are encouraged to design assignments that incorporate AI tools in ways that require students to critically evaluate, analyze, and synthesize AI-generated content, thereby reinforcing intellectual autonomy
- c. Researchers may utilize AI tools to organize data, identify related literature (e.g., Elicit AI), and enhance grammar. However, they must explicitly disclose the extent and manner of AI usage. AI should not be used to interpret research data or write full research proposals or manuscripts. Researchers are encouraged to use AI for editing purposes only, not content creation. Additionally, students are required to submit a Certification of Authorship or Declaration of Originality with their academic outputs.
- d. Staff and administrative offices may use AI tools to enhance efficiency and productivity, provided these tools are used responsibly, ethically, and with appropriate data privacy and security measures.

5. WHAT IS NOT ALLOWED

These actions are not allowed:

- a. Using AI to cheat, copy, or pass off work as your own without saying AI helped.
- b. Making fake research or assignments using AI.
- c. Sharing private information using AI tools without permission.
- d. Using AI to spread lies, hate, or harmful messages.

6. WHO WILL CHECK AND IMPLEMENT THIS POLICY

- a. For class assignments or requirements, all faculty members are responsible for ensuring this policy is followed.
- b. For thesis or dissertation requirements, advisers, research instructors, research coordinators, panel members, and the research center director are responsible for ensuring the policy is followed.
- c. Each department may develop its own specific guidelines aligned with the university-wide policy on the responsible use of Generative AI. Faculty members are encouraged to integrate these guidelines into their course syllabi, ensuring consistency and clarity in implementation. The following elements should be included:
 - c.1 Clearly defined rubrics for assessing student outputs created with the aid of generative AI tools.
 - c.2 Instructions on proper attribution, including specific citation guidelines for AI-assisted content.
 - c.3 A structured class discussion on the benefits and limitations of Generative AI, emphasizing how overreliance may compromise personal learning and critical thinking. This may culminate in formulating a "social contract" that encourages

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students to use Generative AI responsibly—as a support for learning, not a substitute for intellectual engagement.

- d. Anyone who breaks the rules will face consequences according to existing school policies. Violations will be treated as unethical behavior and subject to appropriate penalties. This will be included in the Code of Student Conduct.

7. LEARNING AND TRAINING

To help everyone understand AI better, Saint Mary's University will:

- a. Offer training and workshops about how to use AI properly;
- b. Organize discussions about the impact of AI on people and faith;
- c. Support safe and useful AI use in research, learning, and school operations.

8. CHECKING AND UPDATING THIS POLICY

This policy will be reviewed and updated every two years, or earlier if needed. The review process will follow a hierarchical structure:

- a. Faculty members, department heads, the research center director, and the community extension director may suggest changes or improvements to the policy.
- b. These suggestions will be submitted to the Vice President for Administration and Academic Affairs.
- c. Final recommendations will be forwarded to the Office of the President for approval.

9. POLICY FOUNDATION

This policy is based on the Vision-Mission of Saint Mary's University as a Catholic CICM institution guided by God's wisdom and Christ's mission. It supports SMU's goal of forming individuals who live with faith, strive for excellence, lead with innovation, and serve with compassion.

While the policy was inspired by the AI policies of other member universities of the National Consortium, it was carefully written to reflect SMU's values—faith, learning, service, and responsible innovation.

It aims to guide the use of AI to promote honesty, fairness, and ethical growth, helping shape life-faith integrated persons, compassionate missionaries, globally enterprising leaders, socially engaged professionals, and ethically committed stewards.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Students and teachers use generative AI tools, with ChatGPT (OpenAI) being the most popular. This trend shows that AI is becoming more prevalent in education, emphasizing the need for responsible and ethical use in academic work.
2. The use of generative AI tools is considered to be at a low extent, indicating that while these tools are used, they are not fully integrated into academic activities.
3. AI is being used responsibly, but further efforts are needed to strengthen ethical guidelines and ensure equitable access.
4. Respondents show good adherence to ethical considerations, but there is still a need to maintain academic integrity in the age of AI.
5. AI has a moderate impact on learning and critical thinking. However, it should be used in balance with traditional learning methods to strengthen critical thinking skills.

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6. Most of the universities that responded to the request to include their policies in the review have already established their policies, urging Saint Mary's University to create a clear and accessible policy on the ethical and responsible use of AI to ensure proper guidelines are in place.
7. The proposed AI policy at Saint Mary's University has nine key sections to guide the ethical and responsible use of AI. It focuses on transparency, fairness, and using AI to support academic and administrative tasks. The policy encourages responsible use by students, faculty, and staff, while clearly preventing cheating and misinformation. Monitoring and enforcement will be managed by designated personnel, with regular training to ensure proper use. Based on the university's Catholic values, the policy promotes ethical growth, innovation, and service, with regular reviews to keep it up to date and effective.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The university should evaluate and adopt the proposed policy on the use of AI at Saint Mary's University to ensure it meets the needs of students, teachers, and staff. This is important to guide the responsible and fair use of AI, protect academic integrity, promote balanced use with traditional learning, support real learning and critical thinking, and provide ongoing training and regular policy updates.

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